

Studies on 2,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles. Part-I. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-5-(4'-benzenesulphonamidophenyl)/(4'-pyridyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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Some new 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been prepared having 2-aryl-5-(4'-benzenesulphonamidophenyl)/(4'-pyridyl) moiety. Benzene sulphonamidobenzoyl hydrazide/isoniazide was condensed with different aromatic acids in presence of phosphorus oxychloride. The structures of the compounds were supported by ir spectra. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

1,3,4-Oxadiazole derivatives have been found to possess a wide therapeutic activity¹. With a view to achieving better therapeutic activity, we have synthesised 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (1 and 2).

Benzocaine was condensed with benzenesulphonyl chloride to get 4-benzenesulphonamidoethyl benzoate². It was condensed with hydrazine hydrate to get 4-benzenesulphonamidobenzoyl hydrazide³/isoniazide. The products were treated with different aromatic acids in presence of phosphorus oxychloride to get the respective oxadiazoles. The constitution of the product was supported by ir spectral data.

Ir spectra: The ir spectra (KBr) of the oxadiazole (1), taken on a Spektromon 2000 spectrophoto-

meter, gave the characteristic bands at 1 610 (C=N), 1 125 (C-O-C), 3 200 (NH), 1 355 (SO₂-N asym.), 1 162 (SO₂-N sym.) and 1 295 cm⁻¹ (C-N). The oxadiazole derivatives (2) gave the characteristic bands at 1 640 (C=N) and 1 100 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C).

Experimental

2-Aryl-5-(4'-benzenesulphonamidophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (1). 4-Benzenesulphonamidobenzoyl hydrazide³.

A mixture of 4-benzenesulphonamido ethyl benzoate (3.05 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (2.0 ml, 0.04 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath for 20 h. The resulting solid was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (2.1 g, 70%), m.p. 221° (Found: C, 39.85; H, 3.3; N, 10.70. C₁₈H₁₈N₂O₅S calcd. for: C, 39.89; H, 3.42; N, 10.74%). **2-Aryl-5-(4'-benzenesulphonamidophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles:** A mixture of 4-benzenesulphonamidobenzoyl hydrazide (2.91 g, 0.01 mol), benzoic acid (2.44 g, 0.02 mol) and phosphorus oxychloride (5 ml) was refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol, (3.0 g, 78%), m.p. 154° (Found: C, 63.63; H, 3.95; N, 11.08. C₂₀H₁₈N₂O₅S calcd. for: C, 63.66; H, 3.97; N, 11.14%).

Similarly, other 1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared (Table 1).

2-Aryl-5-(4'-pyridyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (2): A mixture of isoniazide (1.37 g, 0.01 mol), benzoic acid (2.44 g, 0.02 mol) and phosphorus oxychloride (5 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 5 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol, (72%), m.p. 143° (Found: C, 69.88; H, 4.0; N, 18.80. C₁₈H₉N₃O calcd. for: C, 69.95; H, 4.03; N, 18.83%).

Similarly, other 1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE I—DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2*

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
Compound 1				
1.	Phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	154	78
2.	2-Aminophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	205	82
3.	3-Aminophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	210	82
4.	4-Aminophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	195	80
5.	2-Bromophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	154	75
6.	4-Bromophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	238	76
7.	2-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	190	83
8.	3-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	230	75
9.	4-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	127	80
10.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	124	85
11.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	121	72
12.	3-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S	190	72
13.	4-Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S	185	65
14.	3-Carboxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	225	65
15.	3,5-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	168	75
16.	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	193	72
17.	3,5-Dinitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₈ S	165	75
18.	3,5-Dinitro-2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₉ S	155	70
19.	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	162	77
20.	Cinnamyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	209	80
21.	4-Hydroxycinnamyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ S	195	68
22.	3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	222	73
23.	2-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ S	226	69
24.	3-Pyridyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	202	69
25.	4-Pyridyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	240	80
26.	2-Acetylphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	145	75
Compound 2				
27.	Phenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O	143	72
28.	2-Aminophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	97	68
29.	3-Aminophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	110	69
30.	4-Aminophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	230	70
31.	2-Bromophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ BrN ₃ O	150	75
32.	4-Bromophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₃ O	182	70
33.	2-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₃ O	134	65
34.	3-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₃ O	143	68
35.	4-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₃ O	165	72
36.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	150	80
37.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	303	78
38.	3-Nitrophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂	197	70
39.	4-Nitrophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂	204	72
40.	3-Carboxyphenyl	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	252	64
41.	3,5-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	201	70
42.	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	204	74
43.	3,5-Dinitrophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₅ O ₄	168	72
44.	2,5-Dinitro-2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₇ N ₅ O ₅	170	69
45.	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	256	65
46.	Cinnamyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	153	72
47.	4-Hydroxycinnamyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	125	67
48.	3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄	140	68
49.	2-Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	137	65
50.	3-Pyridyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₄ O	221	75
51.	4-Pyridyl	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₄ O	250	68
52.	2-Acetylphenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	109	65

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Antimicrobial activity: The purified compounds were screened for antimicrobial activity using cup-plate method⁴. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 100 µg cm⁻² using DMF as solvent. The compounds were tested against gram-positive

bacteria *S. citris*, *S. aureus* and *S. albus* and gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* and *S. typhosa*. The antifungal testing was carried out with *A. niger* and *Penicillium*. The zone of inhibition of the test solution was measured in mm.

The antimicrobial activity of the compounds was compared with chloromycetin at a same concentration level. From the experimental data, it was observed that most of the compounds showed good activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

The comparable antibacterial activity (zone of inhibition in mm) was observed in compounds 1 and 2 having R = 2-aminophenyl (11–25 mm), 2-chlorophenyl (12–21), 3-chlorophenyl (14–23), 4-chlorophenyl (15–26), 2-bromophenyl (10–30), 4-bromophenyl (12–24), 4-hydroxyphenyl (10–26), 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl (21–26), and 3'-pyridyl (15–24) moiety against *S. aureus* and *S. albus*, and 2-hydroxyphenyl (12–22), 3,5-dinitrophenyl (13–26), 2-aminophenyl (10–20), 3-aminophenyl (12–24), 2-bromophenyl (13–22), 4'-pyridyl (10–22) and 3'-pyridyl (10–24) moiety against *E. coli* and *S. typhosa*.

The comparable antifungal activity was observed in compounds 1 and 2 having R = 3'-pyridyl (23 mm), 3,4,5-trihydroxyphenyl (24), 4-hydroxycinnamyl (23) and 4-hydroxyphenyl (16) moiety against *Penicillium*, and 4-chlorophenyl (20), 4-bromophenyl (21) and 3,5-dinitro-2-hydroxyphenyl (22) moiety against *Penicillium*.

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